

A. C. Polarographic Studies on the Nature of the Capacity Peaks Observed with Organic Compounds at the Dropping Mercury Electrode. Part I. Effect of pH, Nature of the Buffer, and Buffer Capacity

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The effect of pH, nature of the buffer, and buffer capacity on peak potentials and magnitudes of tensammetric peaks as well as reduction peaks, observed with a number of non-ionic organic compounds by a.c. polarography, have been studied. The nature of the buffer, buffer capacity, and pH have practically no effect on the peak potentials of tensammetric peaks, whereas these have pronounced effect on peak potentials of reduction peaks. The variation of peak potential of reduction peaks with pH of the buffer solution is linear and can be used to distinguish the nature of the capacity peaks. The causes of these variations have been discussed.

Gupta¹ studied the effect of pH on peak potentials of a number of organic compounds at the dropping mercury electrode, but no simple characteristics of these substances could be correlated with the observed facts. Breyer and Bauer² also studied the effect of pH on peak potentials of chloranilic acid and *peri*-naphthenone and showed that the peak potential shifted to more cathodic values with increase in pH of the buffer solution.

The present investigation deals with detailed studies of the effect of pH, nature of the buffer, and buffer capacity on the peak potential and the magnitude of the peak observed with a number of organic compounds, which are known to provide tensammetric as well as reduction peaks, with a view to ascertaining the utility of this effect in distinguishing their nature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Organic solid compounds used were either of B.D.H. or Merck's quality and were recrystallised before use, excepting camphor. Organic liquid substances were also pure samples of either Merck or B. D. H. quality and were redistilled in all-glass fractionating column and the middle one-third of the distillate was used for the experiments. Other inorganic chemicals used were of AnalaR quality of B.D.H. Mercury used for the dropping electrode was purified as mentioned in another communication³. Mixtures of (i) KCl + CH₃COONH₄, (ii) KCl + KH₂PO₄ + NaOH, and (iii) KCl + H₃BO₃ + NaOH were used as buffer for acidic, neutral, and alkaline media respectively. The concentration of KCl was

1. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1958, 47A, 254.

2. *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1955, 8, 472, 480.

3. Gupta and Sharma, this *Journal*, to be published later.

maintained 0.1 *M* in all the buffers and the required *pH* was adjusted by adding a few drops of HCl (conc.) or NaOH. The *pH* measurements were made with a glass electrode using a Cambridge bench type *pH*-meter.

The experimental set-up and the technique of measurement were the same as earlier⁵. Negative d.c. potentials were applied to the d.m.e. with respect to the saturated calomel electrode and all the experiments were carried out at a constant temperature of 30° ± 0.5°. The d.m.e. was cathodic throughout the measurements and its constants were: *m* = 4.564 mg./sec., *t* = 1.8 sec. per drop in 0.1 *M*-KCl, open circuit.

TABLE I

Effect of pH on peak potentials and magnitudes of tensammetric peaks in buffered solutions.

50c/s A.C. ripple of ±40 mV (r.m.s.). Temp. = 30° ± 0.5°.

S.No.	Substances.	Conc.	*	<i>pH</i>				
				3.8.	5.2.	7.0.	7.9.	10.0.
1.	Isopropanol	5.0%	A	-1.23	-1.23	-1.22	-1.21	-1.22
			B	37	37	35	35	34
2.	<i>n</i> -Butanol	5.0	A	-1.32	-1.33	-1.32	-1.33	-1.33
			B	161	161	161	169	179
3.	<i>n</i> -amyl alcohol	1.0	A	-1.25	-1.25	-1.25	-1.25	-1.25
			B	165	165	165	165	165
4.	Benzyl alcohol	1.0	A	-1.28	-1.28	-1.28	-1.28	-1.28
			B	150	170	141	141	141
5.	Ether	6.0	A	-1.40	-1.40	-1.40	-1.40	-1.40
			B	214	243	215	243	243
6.	Anisole	Satd.	A	-1.32	-1.32	-1.33	-1.34	-1.35
			B	207	200	183	176	176
7.	<i>o</i> -Cresol	1.0%	A	-1.24	-1.24	-1.24	-1.24	-1.24
			B	159	161	165	162	161
8.	Hydroquinone	0.6	A	-1.04	-1.04	-1.05	-1.05	-1.04
			B	50	51	51	50	51
9.	Pyrogallol	0.6	A	-1.28	-1.27	-1.27	-1.28	-1.27
			B	34	32	31	32	34
10.	Benzoic acid	0.01 <i>M</i>	A	-1.03	-1.05	-1.04	-1.06	-1.06
			B	53	40	45	41	42
11.	Gallic acid	Satd.	A	-1.17	-1.16	-1.17	-1.18	-1.18
			B	51	51	46	41	41
12.	Benzene	Satd.	A	-0.98	-0.96	-0.94	-0.94	-0.96
			B	84	76	70	88	87
13.	Toluene	Satd.	A	-1.05	-1.05	-1.05	-1.03	-1.05
			B	94	94	89	82	94
14.	Aniline	0.1 <i>M</i>	A	-1.28	-1.30	-1.30	-1.30	-1.30
			B	41	89	105	110	115
15.	Camphor	Satd.	A	-1.30	-1.28	-1.28	-1.29	-1.31
			B	204	190	129	172	170
16.	Piperidine	2.0%	A	-1.43	-1.43	-1.44	-1.43	-1.44
			B	50	68	87	66	87

*A denotes peak potential in volts and B, % increase in A. C. in μ A.

TABLE II

Effect of pH on peak potentials and magnitudes of reduction peaks in buffered solutions.

50 c/s A.C. ripple of ± 40 mV (r.m.s.). Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

S.No.	Substances.	Conc.	*	pH				
				3.8.	5.2.	7.0.	7.9.	10.0
1.	Nitrobenzene	$4 \times 10^{-4} M$	A:	-0.43	-0.54	-0.67	-0.74	-0.87
			B:	24	32	110	145	153
2.	o-Nitrophenol	"	A:	-0.42	-0.50	-0.62	-0.70	-0.79
			B:	25	26	43	60	71
3.	m-Nitrophenol	"	A:	-0.43	-0.52	-0.66	-0.73	-0.82
			B:	17	22	80	125	119
4.	p-Nitrophenol	"	A:	-0.46	-0.55	-0.73	-0.81	-0.99
			B:	50	62	86	70	88
5.	o-Nitrobenzoic acid	"	A:	-0.34	-0.41	-0.55	-0.80	-0.87
			B:	6	7	31	48	119
6.	m-Nitrobenzoic acid	"	A:	-0.34	-0.46	-0.62	-0.76	-0.83
			B:	16	25	115	128	128
7.	p-Nitrobenzoic acid	"	A:	-0.35	-0.42	-0.56	-0.70	-0.78
			B:	7	14	51	107	120
8.	p-Nitroaniline	"	A:	-0.53	-0.60	-0.74	-0.82	-0.96
			B:	112	132	141	154	184
9.	3,5 Dinitrobenzoic acid	"	A:	-0.12	-0.40	-0.59	-0.70	-0.77
			B:	5	18	89	128	144
10.	Benzaldehyde	$2 \times 10^{-2} M$	A:	-1.18	-1.24	-1.30	-1.50	-1.47
			B:	482	410	208	163	108

*Same as in Table I.

DISCUSSION

Table I shows the effect of pH in buffered solutions on the peak potentials as well as on the magnitudes of the peaks observed with a number of organic compounds providing tensammetric peaks. Table II records the same data for a number of organic compounds providing reduction peaks. It can be seen in general that the peak potentials of tensammetric peaks are practically constant and do not vary with pH, whereas peak potentials of reduction peaks shift to more cathodic potentials with increase in pH of the buffer solution. This shift of peak potential with pH of the buffer solution is regular and provides a linear curve.

It may be stated that in the case of benzaldehyde, although there is a regular increase in peak potential with increase in pH in the acidic medium, the peak potential remains practically constant with increase in pH in the alkaline medium. Further, there is no regular behaviour of the effect of pH on the magnitude of the tensammetric peaks, but in general it can be seen that with most of the substances studied, the magnitude of such peaks does not vary much with change in pH. The magnitude of the reduction peaks, on the other hand, increases with increase in pH except for benzaldehyde where the magnitude of the peak diminishes with increase in pH. It is also seen in general that the peak potentials of the tensammetric peaks are practically independent of the nature of the buffer and the buffer capacity, whereas the peak potentials of reduction peaks vary with the nature of the buffer and buffer capacity.

The fact that the peak potentials of the tensammetric peaks are independent of the nature of the buffer, buffer capacity, and the pH of the buffer solution indicates once again that such peaks are associated with adsorption-desorption processes at the electrode and the consequent change in the differential capacity of the double layer. Any factor affecting the mercury surface or modifying the surface-active behaviour of organic compounds will have pronounced effect on the position as well as on the magnitude of such peaks. As the nature of the buffer, buffer capacity, and pH produce no such effect, the peak potential of tensammetric peaks remains practically constant. The effect of pH on the magnitude of tensammetric peaks is not regular and no conclusion can be drawn at present, but in most of the cases studied, not much variation in the magnitude of the tensammetric peaks with change in pH of the buffer solution has been observed. Recently we came across a communication⁴ in which the peak potential of phloroglucinol affording tensammetric peak diminished with increase in pH in the alkaline side. We repeated these observations at the same pH values, using the same buffer, and found that contrary to the above observation, the peak potential remained practically constant and was independent of pH . The small variation in peak potential of phloroglucinol with change in pH of the buffer in this case may be ascribed to variations in temperature during the experiment. We have also noticed that the peak potentials of tensammetric peaks vary with change in temperature⁵.

The peak potential of reduction peaks, on the other hand, is almost independent of the pH in unbuffered solution, whereas it shifts to more cathodic value with increase in pH in buffered solutions. It is difficult to explain the cause of this variation as the conditions at the electrode surface are ill defined in unbuffered solution and need further investigation. In buffered solutions, the shift of peak potential regularly to more cathodic values with increase in pH of the system may be due to the fact that hydrogen ions are directly involved in most of the organic reduction processes. As the pH increases, the H^+ -ion concentration decreases and more energy is required for the reduction process. Thus the peak potential shifts to more cathodic values with increase in pH of the buffer solution. This regular increase in peak potentials of the reduction peak with increase in pH of the buffer solutions is linear and can be used to distinguish the nature of such peaks from tensammetric peaks in which the peak potentials are practically constant with increase in pH of the buffer solutions.

The fact that the magnitude of the reduction peaks increases with increase in pH may be due to the increased amounts of organic substances present at the mercury surface at higher pH values, which is supported by the observation that the percentage diminution of the double layer capacity also increases at higher pH values. This is due to the greater extent of adsorption of the organic compounds at the mercury surface at higher pH values as compared to that at low pH values. Benzaldehyde shows discrepancy from the above behaviour at alkaline pH values due to the fact that it exhibits tensammetric peak in alkaline media, which is confirmed by its A.C. polarographic study in non-aqueous media⁶.

It may be concluded that the nature of the capacity peaks observed with such organic

4. Narayan, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1962, 7, 111.

5. Gupta and Sharma, unpublished.

6. Gupta and Sharma, unpublished.

compounds, which are mostly non-ionic in nature, can be distinguished by the effect of pH of the buffered solutions on their peak potentials.

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